

Values of Olfactory Heritage

What role do scents and olfaction play in heritage practices? What are the values connected to historical smells and olfactory practices? Does olfactory heritage merit to be identified, studied and safeguarded, so historical smells can be transmitted to future generations? Should museums, archives and other heritage sites open to olfactory storytelling? What could be the added value of this?

Pilot studies conducted by the Odeuropa project, in collaboration with heritage policy bodies, showed that the values of olfactory heritage and the opportunities that could come with its recognition are manifold.¹ But how can heritage professionals capture these values? The Odeuropa project, in collaboration with cultural heritage institutes and communities, has compiled a list of value statements related to olfactory heritage. These statements can be used by heritage professionals to capture the significance of scents as part of cultural heritage, or to support heritage communities to recognize the role of smell in heritage practices. They can also support GLAMs to capture the added value of working with smells in a heritage context. The value statements can be integrated in questionnaires and interviews. We have ordered them according to various heritages (tangible, intangible heritage, olfactory storytelling in heritage context) and value domains:

Legacy value

- I believe certain smells are valuable as cultural heritage
- Smells / olfactory practices can be significant and are therefore important to preserve for future generations
- It would be a loss if future generations would miss certain smells
- The cultural heritage we want to preserve should reflect different senses (touch, sight, hearing, taste, and smell)
- I would like to visit a museum of heritage smells and learn more about our olfactory past

¹ The research for this resource is described in : Alexopoulos, G. Bembibre, C. and Strlič, M. (2023). *Questionnaires for Measuring the Value of Introducing Smell in GLAMs*. EU Horizon 2020 Technical Report, Odeuropa Project Deliverable D6.2 (journal publication in preparation). Leemans, I., Bembibre, C., Elpers, S.; Mladenici, D., *Odeuropa Policy Brief*. Technical report for the Odeuropa project 2021 (EU Horizon 2020). Elpers, S., Van Duijvenvoorde, J., Jaffe-Schagen, J., Miłkowska, K. and Leemans, I. (2022), 'Geur in immaterieel erfgoed. Een deelonderzoek van Odeuropa.' *Volkskunde* 122:3. Leemans, I. and Verbeek, C. (eds.) (2023), *Neuswijzer: Geuratlas van de Lage Landen*. Amsterdam: Boom.

Intangible heritage practices

- Smells belong to our tradition
- Smells play an important role in my heritage practice
- The use of my nose is important in my craftsmanship
- Smells determine the quality of crafted products we make
- Smells add to the enjoyment of our heritage practice
- Olfactory rituals are important for my religious community
- Smells help to shape our heritage practice into a social event
- Smells heighten the intensity with which we experience our traditions
- When I smell a specific scent, I know the season of our cultural heritage practice is coming up
- I miss smells from the past that are 'lost' (no longer perceivable)

Identity - Sense of belonging - Community value

- I believe that certain smells represent who I am
- Smells help me feel that I belong (or did belong) to a place
- Certain smells / olfactory practices make me feel part of a community
- My region has a specific smellscape. When I perceive this, it feels like coming home

Sense of time, sense of place

- Smells make me feel that I travel in time
- Smells bring images of specific places to my mind
- Smells can help me imagine a place in the past
- I feel connected to the past through the use of my sense of smell
- I believe that smells are a useful source for information about the past
- I would like to be able to smell historical sites or moments in time

Learning value

- When visiting a heritage site, I find it interesting to capture the smell of the site
- If I would be able to smell artefacts in a museum, I would better understand their use and value
- If I could smell artefacts in a museum, the smells would bring the objects and artworks more to life
- Using my nose helps me to better understand heritage objects, places and stories
- Smelling could help me learn more about the materials heritage objects are made of
- Smells in a museum/ historic environment should add something to a story
- Smells can help me discover elements that are not otherwise present or visible in the artworks / heritage site
- Smells can be used to present important issues about the environment
- Smells help me make new connections between objects/ artworks, history and places

Affective value (emotions, feelings, mood)

- Smelling affects my feelings and emotions
- Smells can make me feel overwhelmed
- Smells bring personal memories to mind

Wellbeing

- Experiencing smells makes me feel good about my life
- Experiencing smells can have a positive impact in my mental health

Enjoyment of museum visits

- I enjoy smelling during museum visits / tours
- Smells can make museum visits / guided tours special
- The smells made me feel immersed in the scenes/stories/places
- Smells leave a strong impression to a visit/tour

Participatory value

- Smelling in a museum/ heritage environment encourages me to be active and participate in activities
- Smelling in a museum/ heritage environment encourages me to share my reactions and feelings with other people
- Smelling during a museum visit / guided tour is a good conversation starter

Diversity

- Using smells in a museum/ heritage environment creates opportunities for people with different needs to engage with the collections
- Smells in a museum/ historic environment can make stories / places / objects be meaningful to diverse people
- Including smells in a museum/ heritage environment helps to create different stories about people / places / objects

Authenticity – accuracy

- I would like to be able to smell a museum object / historic place as well as see it
- Scents used in a heritage environment should be exact copies of the authentic ones
- In a museum/ heritage environment, smells that express an idea or an imaginative environment are useful
- Smells in a museum/ heritage environment can be interesting even if they are not exact recreations of how something smelled in the past.

Conservation health and safety

- I am concerned about the impact of smells on objects / collections / historic buildings and materials
- Using smells in a museum/ heritage place is safe for visitors
- I believe that clean air in museums is crucial for heritage preservation

Economic value

- I am more willing to pay for a visit to an exhibition or historic place if there are smells present